

Request for Access to PROJECT Data and/or Samples

A letter approving access to PROJECT data and/or samples will only be issued if this request for access is submitted and approved by the PROJECT Consortium Management Board (CMB). Please complete all sections as indicated.

Applicants are strongly encouraged to make a feasibility enquiry through our Consortium Manager before submitting this form. This is advised in all cases but particularly is required in order to clarify which data and/or samples are being collected by PROJECT and to assess any requirements you may have in respect of PROJECT providing a letter in support of any grant application you intend to submit in respect of your project.

Please note that only access to PROJECT data and/or samples can be authorised through this application. No access will be authorised to any data and/or samples which have been made available to PROJECT from any independent study. Applications for access to data and/or samples outside of the scope of PROJECT will be rejected. The Consortium Manager will discuss this with you when you make your feasibility enquiry.

PROJECT has collected data from multiple studies, but the associated samples remain with the individual studies and PROJECT cannot share those. This form therefore relates to the joined data in PROJECT and a small number of samples that are directly associated with PROJECT. Any requests for biological samples may also be forwarded to their original study to be reviewed and assessed by their respective Steering Committees for eligibility and availability.

1. Contact details of the Contracting Institution:

Name:	
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Organisation URL	
Address:	
Telephone Number:	
Email:	

2. Contact details for principal investigator and other individuals involved in the project:

Name	Title	Department/Institution

3. Title of project:

4. Project start and proposed completion dates:

5. Summary of the project (please provide, in **no more** than 500 words, and in **lay** terms, a clear and simple summary of the proposed project. Include details of study aims, design, methods, timelines and why you require PROJECT data and/or samples. Also, please state how this project fits into any larger study it is or will be part of, or names of your network or groups who will be part of this work (**NOTE**: our aim in asking this question is to assess the degree of overlap with the PROJECT study to try and avoid any conflicts of interest).

6. Current association with PROJECT or any PROJECT investigator(s) *(if applicable)*:

7. Proposed assays *(if relevant)*:

Please list assays and technology platforms to be applied to the data or samples

8. Summary of data analysis plan (max. 250 words). Further details if needed can be included in an annex:

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9. a. Which data and/or samples does your project need to access from PROJECT? **Please update this section further after Feasibility Discussion and access to the PROJECT Data Catalogue and Data Dictionary to capture detailed requirements.**

10.

	Tick if required	Number of items of data, types of samples requested	Sample/data requirements e.g. volumes/cell numbers/amount; sample type; data type; specific areas; and data fields e.g demographics, treatment response, other medication	Country of final sample/data location (if approved)
Clinical Data	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Samples If yes, give details	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Biological Data	<input type="checkbox"/> GWAS <input type="checkbox"/> PBMC RNA-seq <input type="checkbox"/> Cell-sorted RNA-seq <input type="checkbox"/> SF RNA-seq <input type="checkbox"/> SF cell-sorted RNA-seq <input type="checkbox"/> SWATH-MS proteomics <input type="checkbox"/> Flow cytometry Other:		<input type="checkbox"/> raw <input type="checkbox"/> summary stats <input type="checkbox"/> FASTQ <input type="checkbox"/> read counts <input type="checkbox"/> Abundance <input type="checkbox"/> FCS <input type="checkbox"/> gated stats Other:	

b. Are these numbers of samples requested based on a power calculation? Yes/No
If yes, briefly describe your calculations

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11. Project Funding: Will you be making an application to grant bodies to fund your project? If so, please give details, including if this process will involve peer review. If you are not making a funding application then please indicate how your project will be funded.

(Please note that the CMB may request to see the final award letter if funding is granted)

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12. Date of Application

13. All relevant information must be included within this application and must NOT exceed 6 pages of A4 paper (not including the Annexes). Please submit the application form by email plus one original by post (in **single spaced typescript**) to:

PROJECT Consortium Manager
Email: info@PROJECTconsortium.org.uk
Address: INSTITUTION address

If approved, the CMB will issue the PROJECT Access Summary and PROJECT Access General Terms (which includes the PROJECT Authorship guidelines) for signing. A copy of the PROJECT Access Summary and PROJECT Access General Terms is set out at Annex B for your reference.

INSTITUTION shall act on behalf of the PROJECT Consortium to provide the approved access to the requested data and/or samples. Data and/or samples will only be provided by INSTITUTION on the terms set out at Annex B. These terms are non-negotiable. You should not complete and submit an application for access to PROJECT data and/or samples if you do not wish to accept any of the PROJECT Access General Terms. The terms must be executed by the contracting institution prior to any data and/or samples being provided.

The PROJECT CMB will attempt to respond to your request to access data and/or samples within 30 working days upon receipt of your completed access application form. Request for samples may also be passed back to their original study Steering Committees within 30 days for their consideration. However, PROJECT will be unable to guarantee beyond the transfer of request, any timeline of decision by the study Steering Committees.

Please allow enough time if preparing a grant application to funding bodies. If you need a specific letter for your grant application, please give as much notice as possible and contact the PROJECT Consortium Manager to discuss your requirements BEFORE you start to complete the form.

Please note that if we have any queries on your application, a response may take longer.

Declaration

I have read the application guidelines and the PROJECT Access General Terms. I agree to abide by them if the application is successful.

(Signature of authorised representative on contracting institution)

(Date)

Annex A

Further guidance for Applicants

1. A completed application form for access to PROJECT data and/or samples must be submitted to the PROJECT Consortium Manager for consideration. This access application should include a definition of the amounts and types of data and/or samples required, where the samples and/or data will be physically held and processed, plus state if they need matched clinical data. Types and fields of data required should be specified. Only data and/or samples that can be demonstrated as being relevant to a specific project will be released.
2. Access to PROJECT data and samples will only be provided for academic and non-commercial research purposes. Commercial research proposals should not be submitted under an application. If you wish to use PROJECT data and/or samples for commercial purposes then you must contact the PROJECT Consortium Manager. No commercial use of PROJECT data and/or samples will be considered until the project work of the PROJECT Consortium is complete.
3. PROJECT has collected data from multiple studies, but the associated samples remain with the individual studies and PROJECT cannot share those. Requests for access to Samples will be passed back to the original studies for their respective Steering Committees to review the applications. PROJECT does not have the ethics to approve sample requests. PROJECT will not be able to determine or manage the timeframe for decision making by the study Steering Committees, however it does agree to pass on the applications to the original studies within 30 days of receipt.
4. The PROJECT Consortium Manager will only notify the PROJECT Consortium Management Board (CMB) of an application for evaluation if the application requirements have been satisfied.
5. Once submitted for review, an application may take up to 90 working days to process however, PROJECT aim to get an initial response within 30 days of submission. Samples and/or data will not be provided, and consequently work cannot commence, until approval has been granted by the CMB.
6. You will be charged a fee for the PROJECT Consortium providing you with either data or samples. The fee charged will be dependent on the nature and quantity of the data and/or samples requested. The fee payable will be notified to you if your application is successful. You may request an indication of the likely fee in your feasibility enquiry. An invoice will be raised once the PROJECT Access General Terms are signed. All fees must be paid before access will be given.
7. In cases where substantial funding applications are being made in respect of your project, it is expected that provision will be made in your application to provide support costs of PROJECT. In these instances, the CMB should be consulted.
8. All data and/or samples received must be held and used in accordance with the PROJECT Access General Terms. A copy of these terms is set out at Annex B for your reference. It is advised that you have the terms reviewed by your legal department prior to making your application. This will prevent any undue delay should your application be successful. If you do not wish to agree to these terms then do not submit an application.
9. You must provide details of the final location for the data and/or samples. Please note that the data protection terms (set out at section 4) may be varied depending on the location stated.
10. If successful, you will be required to submit reports (on a minimum of an annual basis) to the CMB (via the PROJECT Consortium Manager) whilst the project utilising the PROJECT materials is ongoing.
11. It should be understood that no proposal which replicates prior or concurrent PROJECT work will be accepted.
12. Projects receiving approval will be given a time limitation to access the requested data and/or samples. This time limitation is the last date by which the project should have commenced and the PROJECT data and/or samples requested accessed. After this date, access and availability of data and/or samples can no longer be guaranteed, and you will have to re-request access through the CMB.

- 13. Data and/or samples will not be released by PROJECT until proof of funding (where applicable) is provided to the CMB (via the PROJECT Consortium Manager). You must inform the PROJECT Consortium Manager immediately if your funding application is unsuccessful. If your application is approved but you have no funding for your project then you will have until your access to the data expires to find alternative funding. If after this date you secure funding then you will have to submit another application.
- 14. All publications derived from studies involving PROJECT data and/or samples are subject to the PROJECT Authorship and Publications Guidelines, a copy of which is provided at Schedule 1 to the PROJECT Access General Terms.

FOR INTERNAL USE ONLY

CMB Ref. No.

Feasibility preliminary check:

Check completed

Check completed by:

Name:

Date:

Comments regarding check (including if funding letter required):

Research proposal authorisation by CMB:

Application accepted

Application rejected

Signed (PROJECT Consortium Chair, or delegated responsible individual):

Name:

PROJECT affiliation:

Signature:

Date:

Annex B
PROJECT Access Summary

Commencement Date of project:	[insert day] [insert month] 20[○]
Anticipated completion date of project:	[insert day] [insert month] 20[○]
Access Deadline:	[insert day] [insert month] 20[○]
INSTITUTION (on behalf of the PROJECT Consortium):	INSTITUTION name and administrative address
Recipient:	[insert full legal name], a company incorporated under the laws of [insert jurisdiction] under company registration number [insert number] whose principal place of business is at [insert address] [name of institution], a body incorporated by Royal Charter (number RC xxx), an exempt Charity in England and Wales and a registered charity in Scotland (No. xxx); and whose address is at [insert address]
Recipient Project:	[Title and brief description]
Data to be shared:	[insert description of the data to be supplied under this agreement]
Samples to be shared:	[insert description of the samples to be provided under this agreement]
Reporting obligations	[monthly][quarterly][annual] progress report to be submitted to the PROJECT Consortium Manager.
Name and title of Principal Investigator:	[insert name]
Fees payable	[insert amount]

In consideration of the [sum of £x now paid by the Recipient (receipt of which INSTITUTION hereby acknowledges on behalf of the PROJECT Consortium)][Fees paid by the Recipient], INSTITUTION shall, on behalf of the PROJECT Consortium, provide the Recipient with access to the data and/or samples as set out above, all subject to the PROJECT Access General Terms attached.

For and on behalf of
INSTITUTION

For and on behalf of
[insert full name of Recipient]

Signed

Signed

full name

full name

Title

Title

Date

Date

PROJECT ACCESS GENERAL TERMS

These PROJECT Access General Terms should be read in conjunction with the PROJECT Access Summary, to which these terms are attached. The PROJECT Access General Terms together with the PROJECT Access Summary and any other documents referred therein are collectively referred to as the "Agreement".

[Insert PROJECT access general terms]

Schedule 1
PROJECT Authorship and Publication Guidelines

[Insert PROJECT publication and authorship guidelines]

Schedule 2
PROJECT CONSORTIUM
SAMPLES TRANSFER RECORD

1. **The PROJECT Consortium** has collected and/or developed the samples known as

*Insert description
of Samples*

2. *Insert name
of Requestor*

_____ (the "Requestor") who is an employee of

*Insert name
and address of
Requestor's
Institution*

_____ (the "Institution") and whose address is

and wishes to acquire the Samples for research for the purposes of:

*Insert description
of research project for
which Samples
are to be used*

*If applicable, insert
details of any affiliate
or third party transfer
arrangements*

Whilst the Requestor remains responsible for use of the Samples at all times, it is agreed that the Recipient can transfer the Samples to the following affiliate/third party for the sole purpose of undertaking their research project

3. *Insert quantity of
Materials to be
supplied and period
for which they are to
be provided for*

The Supplying Party is willing to provide (insert quantity) of the Samples to the Requestor on the PROJECT Access General Terms.

HUMAN TISSUE TRANSFER

4. *LOCATION OF LABORATORY WHERE MATERIALS ARE TO BE HELD/USED:*

5. *HTA LICENCE / ETHICS APPROVAL:*

Complete one of the following:

This research project has been given a favourable opinion by an ethics committee which, within the UK, is recognised under the Human Tissue Act 2004. Please provide the reference of the opinion and name of the committee:

Or:

The Samples are to be stored in premises licensed by the Human Tissue Authority, until favourable ethical approval has been obtained for the research project at which point the Requestor shall notify INSTITUTION. Please provide the licence number:

Or:

Where the Samples are supplied by INSTITUTION from a research tissue bank which may be a diagnostic archive and which has been granted REC approval for specific research projects, this REC approval may cover the research project with the Samples at the Requestor Institution. If this is the case, INSTITUTION confirms that its REC approval for the tissue bank will cover the research project by signing here:

.....

INSTITUTION is willing to provide Samples to the Requestor on the terms and conditions set out in the PROJECT Access General Terms.

AGREED by the parties through their authorised signatories:-

For and on behalf of INSTITUTION

**For and on behalf of
[Requestor]**

signed

signed

print name

print name

title

title

date

date